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A Study on Parent's Perception towards Post Office Saving Schemes –With Special Reference to Palayamkottai Region

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ABSTRACT

The Post Office savings bank is the oldest and the largest banking system in India. Savings are vital factors for the growth and improvement of the economy of the country. In India, Post Office savings scheme provides a secure, risk free and attractive investment option for the small investors. Post office savings schemes are one of the modes for them to save their valuable earning. Post offices offer various saving schemes like Savings Bank Account, National Savings Certificate Account, Post Office Monthly Income Scheme, Senior Citizen Scheme, Recurring Deposit, Sukanya Samridhi Account, Ponmagan podhuVaippu nidhi and so on. In this study we mainly focus on the saving schemes for children. This study is conducted to analyze the perception of parents toward Post office saving schemes in Palayamkottai. This study is particularly conducted among the parents because they save major part of their salary for their children's education and marriage. The primary data is collected by developing a well structured questionnaire mainly taking into consideration the objectives of the study. The questionnaire is circulated among 80 respondents and 78 were collected back and 8 were found incomplete. So the sample size is restricted to 70. Simple random sampling method was adopted. While analyzing the primary data, statistical tools such as percentage analysis, Garrett ranking, weighted average method, chi square and t test techniques are used in this study. It is concluded that that parents are highly interested and satisfied in depositing their savings in Post Office Savings scheme.

KEY WORDS: Post Office Saving Scheme, Parent's perception, problems, factors influencing.

INTRODUCTION

The Post Office savings bank is the oldest and the largest banking system in India. It offers the savings products across its 155015 Post offices and the country has been divided into 23 postal circles. The post office savings bank in India was established by the Britishers. Savings are vital factors for the growth and improvement of the economy of the country. In India, Post Office savings scheme provides a secure, risk free and attractive investment option for the small investors. Post office savings schemes are one of the

modes for them to save their valuable earning. The Indian post office helps the people to deposit their money in post office saving schemes for those who do not have a bank in their area. The investment is generally associated with the attitudes, perceptions and willingness of individuals and institutions. Post offices offer various saving schemes like Savings Bank Account, National Savings Certificate Account, Post Office Monthly Income Scheme, Senior Citizen Scheme, Recurring Deposit, Sukanya Samridhi Account, Ponmagan podhuVaippu nidhi and so on. In this study we mainly focus on the saving schemes for children. This study is conducted to analyze the perception of parents toward Post office saving schemes in Palayamkottai. This study is particularly conducted among the parents because they save major part of their salary for their children's education and marriage.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. N.R.Vembu, J.Abinaya & K.Kirubhhaharan (2018) explains that Illiterate people's shows higher amount of interest on investing their money in post office due to lack of awareness and other related factors. Higher income group never interest to invest their money in post office due to low interest rate. Tax relief is also biggest boon for investing their money in post office savings scheme. The officials need to create awareness among the people for investing their money in post office will facilitate the growth of postal sector.

Dr N Rameshkumar (2018) It is one of the best investment schemes for rural working women when compare to other investment schemes. Rural working women investors have a great faith and positive attitude towards post office savings schemes because of there is no complicated procedure in making investment, Easy accessibility, Secure and Safety investment , premature closure etc

Dr. S. Gulam mohamed M. Shajahan (2016), states that the post office has traditionally served as a financial institution for millions of people in the rural areas. It plays a vital role in rural areas. It connects these rural areas with the rest of the country and also provides banking facilities in the absence of banks in the rural areas.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the various post office saving schemes available for children.
- To examine the awareness level and perception of parents towards Post office saving schemes in Palayamkottai area.

- To analyze the factors that influences the parents to prefer post office saving schemes.
- To study the problems faced by the parents while investing in post office saving schemes.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study aims at measuring the level of awareness and the perception of the parents towards post office saving schemes. It also focuses to identify the problems faced by them in investing in post office saving schemes. The result of this study also serves as a basis for additional research in the field of post office saving scheme.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Every research has to face its limitations. Some are controllable and some are not controllable. The limitations of the study are as follows.

- The area of the study is restricted to Palayamkottai only
- This study covers only the parents and post office saving schemes for kids.
- The sample size is restricted to 70.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study is a descriptive survey based study. It is mainly based on primary data and secondary data. The primary data is collected by developing a well structured questionnaire mainly taking into consideration the objectives of the study. The questionnaire is circulated among 80 respondents and 78 were collected back and 8 were found incomplete. So the sample size is restricted to 70. Simple random sampling method was adopted for selecting the respondents. The secondary data is collected through books, manuals and websites.

TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS

The statistical tools help us to evaluate the problems under the study in a judicial manner. While analyzing the primary data, statistical tools such as percentage analysis, Garrett ranking, weighted average method, chi square and t test techniques are used in this study

DATA PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 1: Profile of the respondents

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Up to 25 years	10	14%
	25 to 35 years	27	38%
	35 to 45 years	22	32%
	Above 45 years	11	16%
Gender	Male	43	61%
	Female	27	39%
Educational Qualification	12 th	15	21%
	UG	30	43%
	PG	09	13%
	Others	16	23%
Monthly family income	Less than 20000	13	19%
	Rs 20000 – Rs 30000	27	39%
	Rs 30000 - Rs 40000	22	31%
	More than Rs 40000	08	11%
Savings per month	Below 3000	15	21%
	Rs 3000 – Rs 4000	29	42%
	Rs 4000 – Rs 5000	16	23%
	More than Rs 5000	10	14%
Information about Post office saving schemes	Post office employee	12	17%
	Advertisements	08	11%
	Self interest	27	39%
	Friends&Family members	12	17%
	Agents	11	16%
Perception towards Post office saving schemes	Vital	43	62%
	Essential	07	10%
	Desirable	10	14%
	Cannot say exactly	10	14%
Level of satisfaction	Very high	39	56%
	High	17	24%
	Neutral	08	11%
	Low	04	06%
	Very low	02	03%

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

The above table explains that

- Majority (38%) of our respondents belong to the age group of 25 to 35.
- Majority (61%) of our respondents are male.
- Majority (43%) of our respondents have completed their UG.
- Majority (39%) of our respondents have a monthly income of Rs 20000 to Rs 30000.
- Majority (42%) of our respondents have a monthly saving of Rs 3000 to Rs 4000.
- Majority (39%) of the respondents say that they gather information about post office saving schemes on their own self interest.
- Majority (62%) of the respondents feel that post office saving schemes is vital.

- Majority (56%) of our respondents say that they are highly satisfied with the post office saving scheme

Table 4: Awareness among Parents about Post office saving schemes

Post office saving schemes	Aware		Not aware	
	No of Respondents	% of Respondents	No of Respondents	% of respondents
1. Ponmagan podhu Vaippu nidhi	60	86%	10	14%
2. Post Office monthly income scheme (POMIS)	26	37%	44	63%
3. Suganya samriddhi Yojana	66	94%	04	06%
4. Post office National saving Certificates	54	77%	16	23%
5. Post office recurring deposit	22	31%	48	69%

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

The above table interprets that majority of the respondents are aware of Suganya Samriddhi Yojana and Ponmagan Vaippu Nidhi and majority of our respondents are less aware of Post office recurring deposit and Post office monthly income scheme.

Table 3: Problems faced by Parents in depositing in Post Office saving Schemes

Weighted average method is used to analyze the problems faced by the parents in depositing Post office saving scheme

Statement	Strongly agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Total score	Avg Score	Rank
Inadequate information	50 (250)	6 (24)	6 (18)	4 (8)	4 (4)	304	61	I
Delay in processing	40 (200)	4 (16)	4 (12)	6 (12)	16 (16)	256	51	IV
Lack of agent support	30 (150)	5 (20)	5 (15)	5 (10)	25 (25)	220	44	V
Lengthy formalities	45 (225)	6 (24)	6 (18)	6 (12)	7 (7)	286	57	II
Poor response from employees	35 (175)	5 (20)	5 (15)	10 (20)	15 (15)	185	37	VI

Low return	43 (215)	4 (24)	6 (18)	6 (12)	11 (11)	280	56	III
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Source: Data collected through questionnaire

From the above table it is inferred that majority of our respondents feel that the major problems faced by them are inadequate information about the saving schemes in the post office followed by the lengthy formalities and low return.

Table 4: Factors influencing the Parents to invest in Post Office saving scheme

Garrett ranking method is used to analyze the factors influencing the parents to invest in Post office saving schemes

FACTORS	SCORE	AVG. SCORE	RANK
Risk free investment	3743	53	IV
For children marriage	4636	66	I
For children education	4410	63	II
Promote saving habit	4048	57	III
Tax free	3473	50	V
Friendly approach of employees	3003	43	VI

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

From the above table it is understood that majority of the parents feel that the factors influencing to invest in post office saving scheme are to save for their children marriage followed by to meet out education expenses and to promote saving habit.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H₀1: There is no association between monthly income and the factors influencing the parents to invest in Post office saving schemes.

Particulars	Calculated value	Table value at 5%	Df	H ₀ accepted/ rejected
Chi- square	5.8	24.996	15	Accepted

Since the calculated value (5.8) is less than the table value (15.507) the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no association between monthly income and the factors influencing the parents to invest in post office saving schemes.

H₀2: There is no association between the age and their perception towards post office saving schemes.

Particulars	Calculated value	Table value at 5%	Df	H ₀ accepted/ rejected
Chi- square	31.15	16.919	9	Rejected

Since the calculated value (31.15) is more than the table value (16.919) therefore the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is association between the age of the respondents and their perception towards Post office saving schemes.

H₀3: There is no significant difference between genders in their level of satisfaction

	n	mean	Std deviation	Variance	df	Significance	t stat	t critical two tail
Male	43	4.19	0.82	0.68	57	0.05	0.38	+/- 2.0025
Female	27	4.11	0.80	0.64				

Since the t value (0.38) lies between -2.0025 and +2.0025 we do not reject the null hypothesis. Therefore there is no significant difference between male and female in their level of satisfaction.

SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

- Many of the respondents feel that due to lack of adequate information they are not aware of various schemes of the post office. So the post office department should create awareness about the schemes by conducting awareness campaigns and fairs.
- Majority of the respondents says that the interest rate is low in post office saving schemes. Parents mainly prefer post office saving scheme for their children's marriage and education, so necessary steps should be taken to increase the interest rate.
- In order to overcome the delay in processing the latest technological advancement should be introduced and thereby we can reduce the transaction time.
- Parents prefer post office saving schemes for tax benefit, but tax benefits are attached only to few schemes. Therefore it should be extended to many schemes in near future.

- Poor responses from employees are also considered as a major problem by the respondents. So the special officials should be appointed to monitor the grievances of the customers.
- There is an association between age and their perception towards Post office saving schemes that shows the young parents consider post office saving schemes is vital. So the post office department should take effective steps to attract the aged parents also.

From the above study it is understood that parents are highly interested and satisfied in depositing their savings in Post Office Savings scheme. The main reason for this is the risk free investment and the tax benefits. The above mentioned suggestions should be implemented by post office so that it can improve their performance and thereby we can increase the number of investors in post office saving schemes. There are only few saving schemes were offered by post office for the benefit of children and it should be increased in near future. Many new schemes for children should be introduced by the post office so that the parents can meet out their children's education and marriage expenditure without any difficulties.

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